

Universitatea din Bucuresti Facultatea de Matematica si Informatica

Master: Baze de Date și Tehnologii Software

Proiect

Securitatea bazelor de date

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1. Introducere

1.1 Prezentarea modelului si a regulilor sale

Pentru realizarea acestui proiect am ales ca tema gestionarea unui lant de sali de fitness in cadrul carora se ofera servicii de antrenament precum si evidentierea rezultatelor la anumite intervale de timp.

Operatiunile din baza de date se concentreaza asupra clientilor. Acestia au posibilitatea de a achizitiona abonamente cu durata si preturi diferite. Fiecare sesiune de antrenament se realizeaza individual, cu sau fara indrumarea unui antrenor de fitness.

In baza de date sunt stocate datele specifice antrenorilor, salile de sport unde acestia lucreaza precum si programele de fitness disponibile.

Utilitatea acestui model este acela de monitorizare al rezultatelor, atat rezultatele clientilor individuali dar si al lantului de sali de fitness, intrucat se pot genera rapoarte rezultate/cost pentru clienti cat si rapoarte profit/costuri pentru lantul de sali.

Baza de date contine 10 tabele. In cadrul acestora au fost aplicate 2 constrangeri, constrangerea PRIMARY KEY si constrangerea FOREIGN KEY.

Constrangerea PRIMARY KEY identifica unic fiecare inregistrare. Astfel in fiecare din cele 10 tabele, exista o coloana, prima coloana, definita PRIMARY KEY. Existenta identificatorului unic la nivel de tabel permite operatiuni asupra oricarei inregistrari atunci cand se doreste realizarea de operatiuni asupra acesteia si numai acesteia.

Constrangerea FOREIGN KEY stabileste o legatura pe baza unei chei externe intre o coloana din tabel si o coloana din tabelul referit. In tabelele ce contin date despre achizitii de servicii precum si rezultatele clientilor, sunt folosite chei externe pentru a genera rapoarte individuale despre fiecare client.

1.2 Diagrama Conceptuala

1.3 Schemele Relationale

Customers (customer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues)

Results (result_id, customer_id, body_fat, weight, height, age, entry_date)

Subscriptions (subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days, price)

Customers_Subscriptions(customer_subscription_id, subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price)

Sessions (session_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date)

Trainers (trainer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, birth_date, gender)

Contracts (contract_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date, salary)

Locations (location_id, location_capacity, city_id, address)

Cities (city_id, state_id, city_name)

States (state_id, state_name)

1.4 Crearea Tabelelor (script separat)

2. Criptarea datelor

2.1 Criptare

Datele personale (email si phone_number) ale tabelului **tb_trainers** vor fi criptate (AES- 128, PAD_PKCS5, CHAIN_CBC) și stocate în tabelul **tb_trainers_crypt** astfel:

- pentru antrenorii de gen feminin inregistrarile vor fi criptate cu cheia **cheie_f**
- pentru antrenorii de gen masculin inregistrarile vor fi criptate cu cheia **cheie_m**

Cele doua chei vor fi generate automat si vor fi stocate in baza de date.

Se vor folosi secventa **tb_secv_idcheie** si tabelul **tb_chei** (idcheie#,cheie,tabel)

Si procedura **criptare_trainer_email_phone** fara parametrii.

Afisez cele doua chei folosite pentru criptate:

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window shows a query result for the **tb_chei** table. The query executed was `select * from tb_chei;`. The result set contains two rows of data:

ID_CHEIE	CHEIE	TABEL
1	19F427EEAA432C9C665B28D3D38CE0634	tb_trainers
2	2C905CA64CD29713B0F50B91E825DC488	tb_trainers

The interface also shows the Connections pane on the left, the Reports pane, and the Script Output pane at the bottom, which displays the message: "Trainer email: LydiaRoss100@c.dwb1.com female".

Afisez datele din tabel necriptate.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL query in the Worksheet:

```

307
308   end loop;
309   commit;
310   end;
311   /
312
313   execute criptare_trainer_email_phone;
314
315   select * from tb_chei;
316   select email, phone_number, gender from tb_trainers;
317   select * from tb_trainers_crypt;
318
319

```

The Query Result pane shows the following data:

ID	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	GENDER
1	LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com	1037381919	female
2	MichaelHall101@t.dwb1.com	9026171316	male
3	BeverleyHall102@t.dwb1.com	7601908127	female
4	DanielClarke103@t.dwb1.com	2762164928	male
5	ElaineNelson104@t.dwb1.com	7144098029	female

The Dbms Output pane shows the command: `Trainer email: LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com female`.

Afisez datele din tabel criptate.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL query in the Worksheet:

```

307
308   end loop;
309   commit;
310   end;
311   /
312
313   execute criptare_trainer_email_phone;
314
315   select * from tb_chei;
316   select email, phone_number, gender from tb_trainers;
317   select * from tb_trainers_crypt;
318
319

```

The Query Result pane shows the following data:

ID	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	GENDER
1	65 CED30C024B3D2572661610875E1DC452B059CAE77CC0A664451E9ECA4D0E754	CC9CDS9E0979593005FE76F4BB166B65	male
2	66 E19F051429C90F229F4C7BAF8CC5FA4D15FFDB2A6A69BB6A9B0A72CFC6E580	CC485C90E548FD3482F55CE7043F996A	female
3	67 BB25888B2B951821EA37E39586AF40E67E32CDD6A53BALDCF6D1EBE07D31BABF	6287559DF0885DEBD4FAF4CB46D9737	female
4	68 03EA3D5227E8CCCE14E62E0F8E6D4BC6CC2CE02CCEC525D5BE1AA645823BD1	03C1BAC4E6CFASEB120655DCE3C6E458	female
5	69 F0E647739A2832D3803B483AF4E9F9F4BDED95D3D2DE65CBC5F9DC4F42B315DB	281B8D91C9E7789722AAF27D55288D1	male

The Dbms Output pane shows the command: `Trainer email: LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com female`.

2.2 Decriptare

Datele personale (email si phone_number) din tabelului tb_trainers_crypt vor fi decriptate. Se va folosi procedura [decriptare_trainer_email_phone](#) fara parametrii si cheile stocate in tabelul [tb_chei](#), in aceeași ordine (female, male). Datele decriptate se stocheaza in tabelul [tb_trainers_decrypt](#).

Afisez datele din tabel decriptate.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a PL/SQL script in the Worksheet:

```

356 resultat_phone := dbms_crypto.decrypt(rec.phone_number,mod_operare,cheie);
357
358 insert into tb_trainers_decrypt values ( utl_i18n.raw_to_char(resultat_email,'AL32UTF8'),utl_i18n.raw_to_char(resultat_phone,'AL32UTF8'),rec.
359
360 end loop;
361 commit;
362 end;
363 /
364
365 execute decryptare_trainer_email_phone;
366 select * from tb_trainers_decrypt;
367

```

The Query Result pane shows the following data:

EMAIL_DECRYPT	PHONE_DECRYPT	GENDER
1 VictoriaLane231@t.dwb1.com	5044458466	female
2 LydiaJackson232@t.dwb1.com	9785601725	female
3 DanielCooper233@t.dwb1.com	3076332086	male
4 JuliaJackson234@t.dwb1.com	5213137791	female
5 WilliamClarke235@t.dwb1.com	5909432028	male

The Dbms Output pane shows the execution progress and the final output: "Trainer email: LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com female".

2.3 Hash (MD5)

Se creaza o functie `tb_rezumat_md5` ce returneaza rezumatul hash (MD5) pentru inregistrarea din tabelul `tb_trainers`, corespunzatoare antrenorului cu `trainer_id` egal cu 10. Rezultatul este stocat in variabila bind `tb_rezumat1`.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a PL/SQL script in the Worksheet:

```

380 dbms_output.put_line('Inregistrare concatenata: ' || rec_unit);
381 raw_rec := utl_i18n.string_to_raw(rec_unit, 'AL32UTF8');
382 return dbms_crypto.hash(raw_rec, dbms_crypto.hash_md5);
383 end;
384 /
385
386 --test
387 variable tb_rezumat1 varchar2(500);
388 execute :tb_rezumat1 := tb_rezum_md5(10);
389 print tb_rezumat1;
390
391 update tb_trainers set phone_number = '2335679988' where trainer_id=10;

```

The Query Result pane shows the output of the MD5 hash function:

```

TB_REZUMAT1
-----
E69FB06611CBC19BC6B1E9DA063E82B2

```

The Dbms Output pane shows the concatenated string: "Inregistrare concatenata: 10E11sabethJacksonE11sabethJackson10@t.dwb1.com537623438903-FEB-74female".

Se actualizeaza numarul de telefon al antrenorului cu `trainer_id` egal cu 10 si se creaza un nou rezumat in variabila `tb_rezumat2`.

TB_Rezumati1 : E69FB06611CBC19BC6B1E9DA063E82B2

TB_Rezumati2 : 92347CFD854FFE9EE92E9769A63549EE

Se observa ca dupa actualizarea datelor, functia returneaza un hash diferit.

3.Auditarea activitatilor asupra bazei de date

Auditarea se va realiza prin conectarea utilizatorului predefinit **“hr”** la baza de date pluggable **“orclpdb”**.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL script in the Worksheet area:

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( @sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207
208

```

The Script Output window shows the following output:

```

Session altered.

System SET altered.

NAME          TYPE  VALUE
-----
audit_trail   string DB

```

The bottom status bar indicates "Task completed in 0.062 seconds".

The screenshot shows a terminal window titled "SQL Plus" with the following text:

```

SQL*Plus: Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production on Wed Jun 7 09:52:53 2023
Version 19.3.0.0.0

Copyright (c) 1982, 2019, Oracle. All rights reserved.

Enter user-name: sys as sysdba
Enter password:

Connected to:
Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Version 19.3.0.0.0

SQL> shutdown immediate;
Database closed.
Database dismounted.
ORACLE instance shut down.
SQL> startup;
ORACLE instance started.

Total System Global Area 2566910648 bytes
Fixed Size          9269944 bytes
Variable Size       754974720 bytes
Database Buffers    1795162112 bytes
Redo Buffers        7503872 bytes
Database mounted.
Database opened.
SQL>

```

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, userstest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207
208

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.204 seconds

System SET altered.

NAME	TYPE	VALUE
audit_trail	string	DB
audit_trail	string	DB, EXTENDED

Dbms Output

Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, userstest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207 audit select table;
208 desc dba_stmt_audit_opts;
209

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 2.055 seconds

Audit succeeded.

Name	Null?	Type
USER_NAME		VARCHAR2 (128)
PROXY_NAME		VARCHAR2 (128)
AUDIT_OPTION	NOT NULL	VARCHAR2 (40)
SUCCESS		VARCHAR2 (10)
FAILURE		VARCHAR2 (10)

Dbms Output

Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

3.1 Auditare standard

Se executa o comanda “select” pe tabelul `secbd_ifr.tb_trainers`.

Oracle SQL Developer interface showing a query execution. The query in the worksheet is:

```

225 --
226
227 select objname, userid, sqltext, ntimestamp# from aud$ order by ntimestamp# desc;
228 select audit_option, success, failure from dba_stat_audit_opts;
229 show con_name;
230 audit select table;
231 select audit_option, success, failure from dba_stat_audit_opts;
232 select objname, userid, sqltext, ntimestamp# from aud$ order by ntimestamp# desc;
233

```

The 'Script Output' pane shows the execution details: 'Script Output x Query Result x', 'SQL | Fetched 50 rows in 0.064 seconds'. The 'Query Result' pane displays a table with columns: OBJNAME, USERID, SQLTEXT, and NTIMESTAMP#. The results show 7 rows of audit data for various tables like TB_TRAINERS, NLS_SESSION_PARAMETERS, etc.

Sa se afiseze numarul de comenzi select executate:

-de fiecare utilizator pentru fiecare tabel

-de fiecare utilizator indiferent de tabel

-numarul total de comenzi select indiferent de utilizator si tabel

-se vor lua in considerare doar tabellele denumite **tb_trainers**, **tb_locations**,

tb_customers

Oracle SQL Developer interface showing a query execution. The query in the worksheet is:

```

239 -- se vor lua in considerare doar tabellele denumite tb_trainers, tb_locations, tb_customers
240
241 desc aud$;
242
243 select userid, objcreator, objname, count(*)
244 from aud$
245 where lower(objname) in ('tb_trainers', 'tb_locations', 'tb_customers') and trunc(NTIMESTAMP#) = trunc(sysdate)
246 group by rollup(userid, (objcreator, objname));
247
248

```

The 'Script Output' pane shows the execution details: 'Script Output x Query Result x', 'SQL | All Rows Fetched: 8 in 0.058 seconds'. The 'Query Result' pane displays a table with columns: USERID, OBJSCREATOR, OBJNAME, and COUNT(*). The results show 8 rows of audit data for the specified tables.

3.2 Trigger-i de auditare

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

3.3 Politici de auditare

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

4. Gestionarea utilizatorilor unei baze de date si a resurselor computationale

4.1 Proiectarea configuratiei de management a identitatilor in baza de date (matricile proces-utilizator, entitate-proces, entitate-utilizator)

4.1.1 Utilizatorii principali ai aplicatiei

Utilizatorii aplicatiei sunt:

Clienti – email, numar de telefon

Antrenori – email, numar de telefon

Administrator aplicatie – email

La nivelul tuturor acestor utilizatori, adresa de email este un atribut de identificare. Un alt atribut de identificare il reprezinta numarul de telefon.

4.1.2 Procesele din cadrul aplicatiei

In cadrul aplicatiei exista urmatoarele procese:

P1: Administrare antrenori

P2: Administrare clienti

P3: Administrare contracte antrenori

- P4: Administrare rezultate clienti
- P5: Administrare tip abonament
- P6: Administrare abonamente clienti
- P7: Administrare sesiune de antrenament
- P8: Administrare locatii
- P9: Vizualizare antrenori
- P10: Vizualizare clienti
- P11: Vizualizare contracte antrenori
- P12: Vizualizare rezultate client
- P13: Vizualizare tip de abonament
- P14: Vizualizare abonamente clienti
- P15: Vizualizare sesiuni de antrenament
- P16: Vizualizare locatii

4.1.3 Matricea Proces - Utilizator

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16
Cienti									X			X	X	X	X	X
Antrenori				X		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Administrator	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

4.1.4 Identificarea entitatilor prin modelarea datelor aplicatiei

Sistemul este o platforma pentru administrarea unui lant de sali de fitness.

In sistem pot fi configurate abonamentele pe care clientii le pot achizitiona pentru a beneficia de servicii de antrenament de fitness.

Un abonament poate include una sau mai multe sesiuni de antrenament care se desfasoara la o locatie cu sau fara indrumarea unui antrenor de fitness. Clientii care au probleme de sanatate pot participa la sesiuni de antrenament strict sub indrumarea unui antrenor.

Salile de antrenament se afla in diferite judete si orase, numarul de sali operationale din acestea fiind determinat de volumul de abonamente si sesiuni si capacitatea fiecarei locatii.

Antrenorii lucreaza in baza unor contracte, acestia ofera servicii de antrenament si monitorizeaza rezultatele clientilor.

Schemele Relationale:

Customers (customer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues)

Results (result_id, customer_id, body_fat, weight, height, age, entry_date)

Subscriptions (subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days, price)

Customers_Subscriptions(customer_subscription_id, subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price)

Sessions (session_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date)

Trainers (trainer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, birth_date, gender)

Contracts (contract_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date, salary)

Locations (location_id, location_capacity, city_id, address)

Cities (city_id, state_id, city_name)

States (state_id, state_name)

4.1.5 Matricea Entitate – Proces

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16
Customers		C,R,U,D		R		R				R						
Results				C,R,U,D								R				
Subscriptions					C,R,U,D	R							R			
Customers_Subscriptions						C,R,U,D	R							R		
Sessions							C,R,U,D								R	
Trainers	C,R,U,D		R				R		R							
Contracts			C,R,U,D								R					
Locations							R	C,R,U,D								R
Cities							R	C,R,U,D								R
States							R	C,R,U,D								R

Legenda: C=create, R=read, U=update, D=delete

4.1.6 Matricea Entitate – Utilizator

	Cienti	Antrenor	Administratori
Customers	R	R	C,R,U,D
Results	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Subscriptions	R	R	C,R,U,D
Customers_Subscriptions	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Sessions	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Trainers	R	R	C,R,U,D
Contracts		R	C,R,U,D
Locations	R	R	C,R,U,D
Cities	R	R	C,R,U,D
States	R	R	C,R,U,D

Legenda: C=create, R=read, U=update, D=delete

4.2 Implementarea configuratiei de management a identitatilor in baza de date

Se creaza utilizatori astfel: un administrator, doi antrenori si doi clienti.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface. The 'Worksheet' tab contains the following SQL code:

```

64 create user tb_customer2 identified by tb_customer2 password expire;
65 grant create session to tb_customer2;
66
67
68 desc dba_users;
69 select username, AUTHENTICATION_TYPE, ACCOUNT_STATUS, EXPIRY_DATE, CREATED
70 from dba_users
71 order by created desc;
72

```

The 'Query Result' window displays the following data:

USERNAME	AUTHENTICATION_TYPE	ACCOUNT_STATUS	EXPIRY_DATE	CREATED
1 TB_CUSTOMER2	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
2 TB_ADMIN	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
3 TB_TRAINER1	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
4 TB_TRAINER2	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
5 TB_CUSTOMER1	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
6 USERTEST22_IFR	PASSWORD	OPEN	02-DEC-23	05-JUN-23
7 SECBD_IFR	PASSWORD	OPEN	30-NOV-23	03-JUN-23

Se creaza profiluri de utilizatori pentru utilizatorii antrenori si clienti avand consumul de CPU per apel sa nu depaseasca 90 secunde, sa aiba dreptul la o singura sesiune la un moment dat, timpul de viata al unei parole sa fie de 30 de zile si sa poata gresi parola de maxim 5 ori.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface. The 'Worksheet' tab contains the following SQL code:

```

79 create profile tb_profile_customers limit
80 cpu_per_call 9000
81 sessions_per_user 1
82 password_life_time 7
83 failed_login_attempts 5;
84
85 desc dba_profiles;
86 select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like '%tb%';
87

```

The 'Query Result' window displays the following data:

PROFILE	RESOURCE_NAME	RESOURCE_TYPE	LIMIT	COMMON	INHERITED	IMPLICIT
1 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	COMPOSITE_LIMIT	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
2 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	COMPOSITE_LIMIT	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
3 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	SESSIONS_PER_USER	KERNEL	1	NO	NO	NO
4 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	SESSIONS_PER_USER	KERNEL	1	NO	NO	NO
5 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	CPU_PER_SESSION	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
6 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	CPU_PER_SESSION	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
7 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	CPU_PER_CALL	KERNEL	9000	NO	NO	NO

The screenshot shows the SQL Server Enterprise Manager interface. The left pane displays a tree view of the database schema, including tables like TB_CUSTOMERS, TB_LOCATIONS, TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT, TB_TRAINERS_DECRYPT, TB_TRAINERS1, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, and TBE_LAST_NAMES. The main window shows a SQL query in the Query Builder:

```

87
88
89
90
91
92
93
94
95

```

```

--desc dba_users;
select username, profile from dba_users where lower(username) like 'tb_?';

alter user tb_trainer1 profile tb_profile_trainers;
alter user tb_trainer2 profile tb_profile_trainers;
alter user tb_customer1 profile tb_profile_customers;
alter user tb_customer2 profile tb_profile_customers;

```

The Results pane shows the output of the query:

USERNAME	PROFILE
1 TB_ADMIN	DEFAULT
2 TB_TRAINER1	TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS
3 TB_TRAINER2	TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS
4 TB_CUSTOMER1	TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS
5 TB_CUSTOMER2	TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS

The Dbms Output pane shows the execution of the query:

```

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

```

The screenshot shows the SQL Server Enterprise Manager interface. The left pane displays the same database schema tree view. The main window shows a SQL query in the Query Builder:

```

78
79
80
81
82
83
84
85
86

```

```

alter profile tb_profile_customers limit
cpu_per_call 9000
sessions_per_user 1
password_life_time 30
failed_login_attempts 5;

--desc dba_profiles;
select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'tb_?';

```

The Results pane shows the output of the query:

DEFAULT_COLLATION	IMPLICIT	ALL_SHARD	PASSWORD_CHANGE_DATE
VARCHAR2(1100)	VARCHAR2(3)	VARCHAR2(3)	DATE

The Dbms Output pane shows the execution of the query:

```

Task completed in 0.111 seconds
Profile_TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS altered.

```

Se blocheaza temporar accesul utilizatorului **tb_customer1** la baza de date.

Se deblocheaza accesul utilizatorului **tb_customer1** la baza de date.

Se creaza 3 grupuri de consum: **trainers**, **customers**, **other_groups** cu cote de consum de CPU 40%, 20%, respectiv 10%.

5. Privilegiile si roluri

5.1 Privilegiile sistem si obiect

5.1.1 Privilegiile sistem

Se acorda privilegiul de “**select any table**” pentru utilizatorul **tb_admin**.

5.1.2 Privilegiu obiect

Se acorda privilegiu de “select” pe tabelul `secbd_ifr.tb_customers` pentru utilizatorul `tb_trainer1`.

```
Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL>
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane shows a tree view with 'secbd_ifr' selected, containing 'Tables (Filtered)' and 'Indexes'. The main 'Worksheet' area contains the SQL statement: `grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers to tb_trainer1;`. Below the worksheet, the 'Script Output' pane shows the message 'Grant succeeded.' and 'Task completed in 0.073 seconds'. The 'Dbms Output' pane at the bottom shows the session 'secbd_ifr' and 'usertest22_ifr'. The 'Compiler - Log' pane is empty.

```
Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer1@orclpdb
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;

COUNT(*)
-----
       3872

SQL>
```

5.2 Ierarhii de privilegii

Se revoca privilegiul de “select” pe tabelul `secbd_ifr.tb_customers` pentru utilizatorul `tb_trainer1`.

The screenshot displays the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing the database structure, including the `secbd_ifr` schema and its tables.
- Worksheet:** The main area contains a SQL script with the following lines:

```
177 grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_trainers to userstest22_ifr;
178 select * from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;
179
180
181 grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers to tb_trainer1;
182
183 REVOKE select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers from tb_trainer1;
184
185
```
- Script Output:** Below the script, the output shows:

```
Grant succeeded.
Revoke succeeded.
```
- Dbms Output:** A panel at the bottom left showing the execution context: `secbd_ifr` and `userstest22_ifr`.
- Compiler - Log:** A panel at the bottom right showing the compilation status.

```
Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;

COUNT(*)
-----
        3872

SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL>
```

5.3 Privilegii asupra obiectelor dependente

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

5.4 Roluri

Se acorda rolul "**afisare_date**" utilizatorului **tb_trainer2**

Rolul permite privilegiul de "**select**" pe tabelele **secbd_ifr.tb_customers** si **secbd_ifr.tb_locations**.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The 'Connections' pane on the left shows a tree view with 'secbd_ifr' selected. The 'Worksheet' pane contains the following SQL script:

```

187
188 create role afisare_date;
189 grant afisare_date to tb_trainer2;
190 grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers to afisare_date;
191 grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_locations to afisare_date;
192
193 SELECT * FROM DBA_role_privs;
194
195

```

The 'Query Result' pane displays the output of the SQL script, showing a table with 7 rows and 8 columns:

GRANTEE	GRANTED_ROLE	ADMIN_OPTION	DELEGATE_OPTION	DEFAULT_ROLE	COMMON	INHERITED	
1 USERTEST22_IFR	RESOURCE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	
2 SYS	AFISARE_DATE	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	
3 PDB_DBA	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	
4 HR	RESOURCE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	
5 TB_TRAINER2	AFISARE_DATE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	
6 SECBD_IFR	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	
7 USERTEST22_IFR	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	

The 'Script Output' pane shows the following text:

```

+-----+
| GRANTEE | GRANTED_ROLE | ADMIN_OPTION | DELEGATE_OPTION | DEFAULT_ROLE | COMMON | INHERITED |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| 1 USERTEST22_IFR | RESOURCE | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 2 SYS | AFISARE_DATE | YES | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 3 PDB_DBA | CONNECT | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 4 HR | RESOURCE | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 5 TB_TRAINER2 | AFISARE_DATE | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 6 SECBD_IFR | CONNECT | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
| 7 USERTEST22_IFR | CONNECT | NO | NO | YES | NO | NO |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+

```

The screenshot shows a Command Prompt window titled 'Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb'. The output of the SQL*Plus session is as follows:

```

COUNT(*)
-----
3872

SQL> disconnect
Disconnected from Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Version 19.3.0.0.0
SQL> connect tb_trainer2/tb_trainer2@orclpdb
ERROR:
ORA-28001: the password has expired

Changing password for tb_trainer2
New password:
Retype new password:
Password changed
Connected.
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;

COUNT(*)
-----
3872

SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_locations;

COUNT(*)
-----
70

SQL>

```

6. Aplicatii pe baze de date si securitatea datelor

6.1 Contextul aplicatiei

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

6.2 SQL Injection

Se testeaza securitatea datelor prin securizarea si validarea operatiunilor de login ale utilizatorilor din tabelul **tb_trainers** pentru aceasta, se va adauga o noua coloana in **tb_trainers** ce va include parolele de login criptate ale acestora.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The 'Connections' pane on the left displays a tree view of the database schema, including tables like **PHONE_NUMBER**, **BIRTH_DATE**, **GENDER**, **TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT**, **TB_TRAINERS_DECRYPT**, **TB_TRAINERS1**, **TBE_FIRST_NAMES**, **TBE_HEALTH**, and **TBE_LAST_NAMES**. The 'Script Output' pane shows the execution of the following SQL statement:

```
grant alter any table to secbd_ifr;
```

The output indicates that the grant was successful, with the message: "Grant succeeded."

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The 'Script Output' pane shows the execution of the following SQL statement:

```
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD Password varchar(255);
```

The output indicates that the table was successfully altered, with the message: "Table TB_TRAINERS altered."

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane is open, displaying a tree view of database objects including tables like TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT, TB_TRAINERS_DECRYPT, and TB_TRAINERS1, as well as Views, Indexes, Packages, Procedures, and Functions. The main workspace is in 'Query Builder' mode, showing a PL/SQL script with the following code:

```

433
434 create or replace procedure criptare_parola is
435 cheie varchar2(6) := 'parola';
436 raw_text raw(250);
437 raw_cheie raw(250);
438 mod_operare pls integer;
439 rezultat raw(250);
440 cursor c_trainers is select trainer_id from tb_trainers;
441 parola varchar2(100) := 'secret_password';
442 parola2 varchar2(100) := 'secret_password';
443 cnt number := 1;

```

Below the script, the 'Script Output' pane shows the execution results:

```

Task completed in 0.096 seconds
-----
the application administrator or DBA for more information.
Procedure CRIPTARE_PAROLA compiled

```

The 'Dbms Output' pane at the bottom shows the connection name 'secbd_fr' and 'usertest22_fr'. The 'Compiler - Log' pane is empty.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface after the procedure has been executed. The 'Query Builder' workspace now contains the following code:

```

454 cnt := cnt + 1;
455
456 UPDATE tb_trainers SET password = rezultat WHERE trainer_id = rec.trainer_id;
457 --dbms_output.put_line (rezultat);
458 end loop;
459 commit;
460 end;
461
462 execute criptare_parola;
463
464 select * from tb_trainers;

```

The 'Script Output' pane shows the execution results:

```

Task completed in 0.196 seconds
-----
PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

```

The 'Dbms Output' pane at the bottom shows the connection name 'secbd_fr' and 'usertest22_fr'. The 'Compiler - Log' pane is empty.

Connections: Welcome Page, local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

454 cnt := cnt + 1;
455
456 UPDATE tb_trainers SET password = resultat WHERE trainer_id = rec.trainer_id;
457 --dbms_output.put_line (resultat);
458 end loop;
459 commit;
460 end;
461
462 execute criptare_parola;
463
464 select * from tb_trainers;

```

Script Output x Query Result x

SQL | Fetched 50 rows in 0.007 seconds

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER	PASSWORD
1	100 Lydia	Ross	LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com	1037391919	23-AUG-79	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45841FA8A5069FD5471
2	101 Michael	Hall	MichaelHall101@t.dwb1.com	9026171316	30-SEP-78	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458A0915E42DEED983E
3	102 Beverley	Hall	BeverleyHall102@t.dwb1.com	7601908127	07-FEB-75	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458A66B36DA0D42FFF
4	103 Daniel	Clarke	DanielClarke103@t.dwb1.com	2762164928	01-MAR-76	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C4580C39D267106865C4

Dbms Output | Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

M... Logging Page | Statements | Compiler

| Line 464 Column 27 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Connections: Welcome Page, local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr, TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

466 create or replace FUNCTION criptare_parola_v2(parola2 IN VARCHAR2) RETURN VARCHAR2 as
467 cheie varchar2(6) := 'parola';
468 raw_text raw(250);
469 raw_cheie raw(250);
470 mod_operare pls_integer;
471 resultat raw(250);
472 begin
473 mod_operare := dbms_crypto.encrypt_des + dbms_crypto.pad_zero + dbms_crypto.chain_ebc;
474 raw_text := utl_i18n.string_to_raw ( parola2, 'AL32UTF8');
475 raw_cheie := utl_i18n.string_to_raw (cheie, 'AL32UTF8');
476 resultat :=dbms_crypto.encrypt(raw_text, mod_operare,raw_cheie);

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.089 seconds

Function CRIPTARE_PAROLA_V2 compiled

Dbms Output | Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

```

COUNT (*) FROM tb_trainers WHERE email='LydiaRoss100@t.dwb1.com' AND PAROLA=criptare_parola('secret_password1')
CAREA A REUSIT

```

Compiler - Log

M... Logging Page | Statements | Compiler

| Line 479 Column 2 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Se observa ca prima executie a fost validata cu succes, in timp ce a doua, pentru ca s-a folosit aceeași parola ca la prima executie, a esuat, intrucat parolele celor doi antrenori sunt diferite.

Se observa ca executiile au fost validate cu success desi la prima incercare utilizatorul nu stia parola, iar la a doua, nu stia nici adresa de email, nici parola.

Se observa ca executiile nu au fost validate cu succes intrucat la prima incercare utilizatorul nu stia parola, iar la a doua, nu stia nici adresa de email, nici parola.

7. Mascarea datelor

Se utilizeaza mascarea datelor pentru coloana **email** din tabela **tb_trainers**.

Connections: userstest22_jfr

Tables (Filtered): MATERIE, REZOLVA, STUD 1, STUDENT, TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT, TB_TRAINERS_DECRYPT

Reports: All Reports, Analytic View Reports, Data Dictionary Reports, Data Modeler Reports, OLAP Reports, TimesTen Reports, User Defined Reports

```

399
400 :select * from tb_trainers;
401
402 create or replace package pachet_mascare2 is
403 function f_mascare2(sir varchar2) return varchar2;
404 end;
405
406
407 create or replace package body pachet_mascare2 is
408 function f_mascare2(sir varchar2) return varchar2 is
409 v_sir varchar2(100);

```

Script Output: Task completed in 0.343 seconds

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Inregistrare concatenata: 10ElizabethJacksonElizabethJackson10@t.dwb1.com537623438903-FEB-74female

Inregistrare concatenata: 10ElizabethJacksonElizabethJackson10@t.dwb1.com233567998803-FEB-74female

Compiler - Log

Package FACHET_MASCARE2 compiled

Click on an identifier with the Control key down to perform "Go to Declaration"

Line 405 Column 2 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Connections: userstest22_jfr

Tables (Filtered): TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT, TB_TRAINERS_DECRYPT

Reports: All Reports, Analytic View Reports, Data Dictionary Reports, Data Modeler Reports, OLAP Reports, TimesTen Reports, User Defined Reports

```

408 function f_mascare2(sir varchar2) return varchar2 is
409 v_sir varchar2(100);
410 v_lung number;
411 begin
412 v_sir := substr(sir,1,1);
413 select length(sir) into v_lung from dual;
414 v_sir := rpad(v_sir,v_lung,'');
415 return v_sir;
416 end f_mascare2;
417 end;
418 /

```

Script Output: Task completed in 0.162 seconds

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Inregistrare concatenata: 10ElizabethJacksonElizabethJackson10@t.dwb1.com537623438903-FEB-74female

Inregistrare concatenata: 10ElizabethJacksonElizabethJackson10@t.dwb1.com233567998803-FEB-74female

Compiler - Log

Package Body FACHET_MASCARE2 compiled

Utilizati pachetul **pachet_mascare2** si functia **f_mascare2** pentru a masca adresele de email din tabelul **tb_trainers**.

Realizez export-ul tabelului aplicand functia de mascare din pachet in directorul [dirsecbd_ifr](#).

Realizez importul datelor din directory-ul **dirsecbd_ifr** in tabelul **tb_trainers1**.

```

Command Prompt
Job "SECBDFR"."SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01" successfully completed at Mon Jun 5 21:27:44 2023 elapsed 0 00:00:36

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>impdp secbd_ifr/secbd_ifr@orclpdb directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.DMP TABLES=tb_trainers remap_table=tb_trainers:tb_trainers1

Import: Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production on Mon Jun 5 21:30:28 2023
Version 19.3.0.0.0

Copyright (c) 1982, 2019, Oracle and/or its affiliates. All rights reserved.

Connected to: Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Master table "SECBDFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01" successfully loaded/unloaded
Starting "SECBDFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01": secbd_ifr/*****@orclpdb directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.DMP TABLES=tb_trainers remap_table=tb_trainers:tb_trainers1
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE_DATA
. . imported "SECBDFR"."TB_TRAINERS1" 38.98 KB 438 rows
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/CONSTRAINT/CONSTRAINT
ORA-31684: Object type CONSTRAINT:"SECBDFR"."TB_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL" already exists

ORA-31684: Object type CONSTRAINT:"SECBDFR"."TB_TRAINERS_ID_PK" already exists

Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/INDEX/STATISTICS/INDEX_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/TABLE_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/MARKER
Job "SECBDFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01" completed with 2 error(s) at Mon Jun 5 21:30:57 2023 elapsed 0 00:00:28

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, a tree view displays the database schema, including tables like TB_TRAINERS1 and TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT. The main window shows a SQL script in the Query Builder:

```

421 cursor crs is select first_name, last_name, email from tb_trainers;
422 BEGIN
423   for rec in crs loop
424     dbms_output.put_line (rec.first_name || ' ' || rec.last_name || ' ' || pachtet_mascare2.f_mascare2(rec.email));
425   end loop;
426 END;
427
428 execute run_pachtet_mascare2;
429
430 select * from tb_trainers1;
431

```

Below the script, the 'Query Result' pane displays the following data:

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER
1	100 Lydia	Ross	L*****	1037381919	23-AUG-79	female
2	101 Michael	Hall	M*****	9026171316	30-SEP-78	male
3	102 Beverley	Hall	B*****	7601908127	07-FEB-75	female
4	103 Daniel	Clarke	D*****	2762164928	01-MAR-76	male

The 'Dbms Output' pane shows the output of the PL/SQL script, displaying the names and masked emails of the trainers:

```

Lydia Ross L*****
Michael Hall M*****
Beverley Hall B*****
Daniel Clarke D*****
Elaine Nelson E*****

```